

TECHNOLOGY-BASED INITIATIVES AND ADOPTION CHALLENGES IN REDUCING FOOD LOSSES: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW AND PROPOSED CONCEPTUAL MODEL

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Abstract

This study aims to increase our understanding of the technology-based initiatives, adoption challenges in reducing food losses in developed and developing economies countries. A systematic literature review using PRISMA Protocol has been conducted to analyze the 53 articles published from 2012 to 2021. The technology used in developed countries is the latest technology which mostly applies to autonomous systems, while in developing countries, automation systems that still considers human involvement are still applied. Lack of awareness, competency, and infrastructure are the main challenges in adopting technology to reduce food losses in developing countries, while technical risk, market risk, and financial risk are factors to be considered in developed countries. Authors therefore propose a conceptual model to be simulated further in future studies, especially in developing countries.

Keyword: Food Losses; Technology Adoption; Systematic Literature Review

INTRODUCTION

The issue of food losses has been critical in food supply chain management since the waste volume, according to the FAO, reaches 1.3 billion tons per year, especially for perishable products. One of 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), namely SDG 12.3, stated that by 2030, half per capita global food losses along production and food supply chain and waste at the retail and consumer levels have to be reduced. Studies had been conducted to identify the drivers of food losses (Gunasekera et al., 2017; Gardas et al., 2018; Porter et al., 2018; Raut et al., 2019; Despoudi, 2021; Magalhaes et al., 2020), initiatives, and barriers to reducing them (Gadde and Amani, 2015; Chandrasekaran and Ranganathan, 2017; Gokarn and Kuthambalayan, 2017; Parashar et al., 2020; Rodrigues et al., 2020; Despoudi, 2021). Furthermore, the food losses issue may also affect food security and sustainability (HLPE, 2014), which has social, economic and environmental parameters on their impact. According to FAO (2011), food losses or food waste is a quality or quantity degradation of food agricultural products in every stage of the food supply chain, from 'farm' for the production process to 'fork', the process of consumption on the customer's plate. FAO studies have revealed that the rate of food losses and waste (FLW) has reached one-third of the total food produced per year in the food supply chain. Ironically, a large number of people in the world

have to survive hunger or do not have enough food for an active and healthy life, therefore, in maintaining food availability, the flow in the food supply chain must be evaluated in order to avoid high FLW rates, especially in developing countries. For simplification in this study, the term for developed countries is mentioned as North countries, and South countries will be the term for developing countries. The FLW figures for various types of food are different in the North and in the South, due to some differences in the weather and temperature, the availability of infrastructures and technology, and the food chain actors' knowledge and capacity. The difference requires different initiatives in each food supply chain to control the FLW along the chain. Empirical studies based on field observations were considered potential materials for conducting literature review studies to obtain a rich picture of FLW phenomena. In order to devise a solution to reduce FLW, De Gorter et al. (2020) stated in his study that the same initiatives do not always have the same impact on all commodities and countries. These differences also occur in developing countries and countries with more modern inhabitants. Haji et al. (2020) conveyed in the results of his study on 137 papers that technology implementation improves food supply chain efficiency and sustainability by maintain the freshness of food with limited shelf life. Moreover, this study shows the difference between the North and South countries as a reference for developed and developing economies countries regarding the technology used and implementation challenges. The gap between the two cluster types of countries can be considered in future initiatives to improve FLW performance through technology adoption along the food supply chain, especially in developing economies countries. In line with the current wave of technology triggered by pandemics, the use of technology in food supply chain is also increasing. Nonetheless, from previous studies, only a few articles analyze technology adoption in developing countries in terms of reducing FLW, and no studies have compared technology-based initiatives in North and South countries. Hence, this study intends to fill the research gap and addresses the following research questions: (i) what are the technology-based initiatives in North and South countries to prevent and minimize FLW? (ii) What are the challenges of technology adoption faced by North and South countries? (iii) What are the trends of future study directions in FLW reduction? This literature review is divided into five sections to address all research questions and provide recommendations for further research. Section 2 presents the literature review methods and Section 3 presents the results and discussion related to the findings from previous studies. The proposed conceptual model, which maps the cause-effect relationships between elements in a system dynamics model which affects the rate of technology adoption, is described in Section 4, while section 5 presents the conclusions and research limitations.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study applies a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach based on high-standing journal papers to rely on reliable sources of information. As a result, 611 academic articles in the last ten years (2012-2021) were collected and archived from the Scopus and Google Scholar databases, which are known as reputable sources for academic literature. Our search was limited to scientific articles published in reputable journals, excluding other bibliographic materials, such as book chapters, dissertations, conference papers, and other articles, to

guarantee the high quality of the documents. The subject area of the articles was limited to Business and Management because it was within the scope of the analysis. The keywords used were technology AND (“food loss” OR “food waste”) AND (“agricultur* supply chain” OR “food supply chain”). The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines were employed to systematically identify and assess all articles, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Stage of Articles Selection Based On Prisma Protocol

In the first stage, 502 English-written articles were identified from Scopus, and 109 additional articles from Google Scholar that met our keywords. The next stage was to screen the articles. The first step in screening process was to eliminate the duplicate articles from another database (172 articles). The exclusion of 338 articles outside the scope by title and abstract was then conducted to remove articles with less focus on major topics in the content of abstracts. To better align the research questions with the contents of the selected papers, an assessment was conducted by full-text reading and evaluating the 101 articles. Some articles (48) were removed because they did not provide information or analysis related to the research questions as a criterion for the eligibility of articles to be analyzed in this study. After the final process, a set of 53 articles were obtained, and no studies were excluded based on quality.

To obtain the initiatives and adoption challenges in the North and South countries, the first step was to identify the North and South countries. The classification was based on their GDP, as stated in the UN Standard for developed and developing economies countries. We obtained 30 publications that studied North countries, 20 that studied South countries, and 3 articles that described both North and South countries. The figures of FLW in North and South obtained from several articles, described the differences in the location of losses along food supply chain in the two types of countries.

All articles downloaded from Scopus and Google Scholar were processed using the VOS Viewer application to obtain future research directions related to FLW. The visualization of all the author keywords related to technology adoption in reducing FLW and the network between them helped us described the trend of the study. A research gap was also identified from the

results of this map, which can be used as an idea for future research. The conceptual model was then built based on the factors that influence technology adoption.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the FAO, food losses and waste are the decreases in food quantity or quality along the food supply chain. FLW affects sustainable food systems and has a significant effect on food security (Capone et al., 2017). Table 1 describes the causes of FLW that are beneficial as a basis for FLW improvement.

Table 1: Factors Causing FLW

Cluster	Factors	Reference
Food handling	Food handling processes, including the performance of operational processes, packaging mechanisms, and handling during food transportation	Chauhan et al. (2021)
Infrastructure	The quantity and quality of infrastructure, including storage and processing facilities in logistics	Magalhaes et al. (2020); Gardas et al. (2018); Raut et al. (2019); Despoudi (2021)
Capabilities	The capabilities of supply chain actors to adopt technologies	Raut et al. (2019); Gunasekera et al. (2017)
Supply chain uncertainties	Supply chain uncertainties, including climate change, changing customer needs, demands for the aesthetic appearance of foodstuffs, regulatory changes, and the number of intermediary agents	Gardas et al. (2018); Despoudi (2021); Porter et al. (2018)

As described in Table 2, several initiatives in previous studies had been used as alternatives to optimize FLW rates in the food supply chain. The initiatives were classified into three clusters: technology adoption implementation, government intervention, and capability enhancement of supply chain actors.

Table 2: FLW Reducing Initiatives

Cluster	Initiatives	Reference
Technology adoption implementation	Use of technology according to different food characteristics	Gokarn & Kuthambalayan (2017)
	System improvement (forecasting, ordering, distribution)	Parashar et al. (2020); Rodrigues et al. (2020); Despoudi (2021); Chandrasekaran & Ranganathan (2017)
	Improvement in logistics and infrastructure area	Parashar et al. (2020); Gokarn & Kuthambalayan (2017); Gadde & Amani (2016)
Government intervention	Government intervention related to FLW improvement through regulations and programs	Parashar et al. (2020); Gokarn & Kuthambalayan (2017)
Capability enhancement of supply chain actors	Increasing the ability and expertise of supply chain actors, especially in food management from upstream to downstream of the food supply chain	Despoudi (2021)

Bibliometric Analysis

Several publications have documented technology adoption in various parts of the supply chain, and the most frequently cited publication (Lin et al., 2013) documented the utilization of food waste for the production of chemicals, materials, and fuels (see Fig.2). The results contribute to the development of renewable energy that is utilized by the industry, although the production scale is still limited. This study also emphasized food waste valorization rather than conventional food waste processing. The proposed process to increasing value of food waste is an opportunity for the food industry to reduce waste while reducing energy costs by converting food waste as the output of some processes into energy input. The second most-cited article (Mirabella et al., 2013) also has a valorization topic for food waste. The reuse of waste as raw material for new products is related to industrial ecology concepts, such as the circular economy. The concept of a circular economy which is in line with the sustainability concept is a preferred topic recently.

Figure 2: The Most Cited Articles (20 Articles)

As shown in Fig.3, the diagram describes the distribution of 53 published articles, the number of publications decreased from 2013 to 2016; however, we again have an increasing number of articles in the 2017-2020 range. As most of the studies selected are empirical studies in the food supply chain, the pandemic has hampered the data collection process in the field. This may be the reason for the declining number of publications by 2021.

Figure 3: Distribution of Publications on Technology-Based Initiatives in Reducing FLW (2012-2021)

Regarding countries or regions, most studies were conducted in Europe (31), as shown in Table 3. The number of publications was evenly distributed in some European countries and some developing countries, and most studies (8) were located in Italy. Different conditions were found in the results of studies conducted in Asia and Africa. The study objects were limited to Bangladesh, China, Hong Kong, and India, with the largest number of studies in India (9). Studies in Africa are also limited to Ethiopia and Sub-Saharan.

Table 3: Publication Performance Based On Study Location

Regional	Countries	Publications	Reference
Africa	Sub Saharan	2	Lin et al. (2013), Tedla et al. (2019)
Asia	China, India, Bangladesh, Hongkong	14	Gardas et al. (2018), Raut et al. (2019), Lin et al. (2013), Liu et al. (2021), Shashi et al. (2020), Al Amin et al. (2021), Tsang et al. (2020), Chan et al. (2020), Li et al. (2019), Kumar et al. (2020), Balamurugan et al. (2020), Priyardashi et al. (2019) Kaur (2021), Kumar et al. (2021)
Australia	Australia	1	Wikstrom et al. (2013)
Europe	Denmark, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, UK	31	Rodrigues et al. (2020), Lin et al. (2013), Mirabella et al. (2013), Li et al. (2019), Moller Christensen et al. (2019), Oltra-Mestre et al. (2020), Mullick et al. (2020), Moltene & Orsato (2020); Rossi et al. (2021), Ciulli et al. (2019), Cane & Parra (2020), Ruggieri et al. (2020), Garre et al. (2020), De Corato & Cancellara (2019), Bottani et al. (2018), Fabbri et al. (2018), Ribeiro et al. (2018), Bogataj et al. (2017), Li & Wang (2017), Andreopoulou (2017), Salinas Segura et al. (2017), Liljestrang (2016), Haass et al. (2015), Bertolini et al. (2013), Simms et al. (2019), Kamilaris et al. (2019), Pfaltzgraff et al. (2013), Kamble et al. (2019), Lanfranchi et al. (2016), Paulikiene et al. (2020), Gruzauskas et al. (2019)
Middle East	Qatar	1	Irani et al. (2018)
US	Brazil, Columbia	5	De Souza et al. (2021), Gustavo et al. (2021), Orjuela-Castro et al. (2019), Kamath (2018), Yu & Nagurney (2013)

Considering the large cost required to conduct FLW research, most studies in South countries are funded by third parties, such as non-profit institutions or extension organizations of the United Nations, which play a role in sustainable global food security

Fig.4 shows the ten major journals that published topics related to this study. The four journals with the largest number of publications on the subject were The Journal of Cleaner Production, An International Journal, and International Journal of Production Research. The remaining journals had the same number of publications (2). The Journal of Cleaner Production had the highest number of publications (13). It emphasized green marketing, forecasting accuracy, green supply chains, environmental improvement, and sustainability.

Figure 4: Publication Performance Based on Journals

DATA ANALYSIS

Based on the research questions of this study, the following analysis will explain and interpret the data obtained from the 53 selected articles.

The technology-based initiatives in North and South Countries

As Table 4 shows, the initiatives are clustered based on the area of improvement, describing the food supply chain process in an industry.

Table 4: Technology Applied In Initiatives in North Countries (Australia, Denmark, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Qatar, Spain, Sweden, Uk, Us)

Numbers of Publications	Reference	Technology applied in initiatives	Cluster of Technology
1	Moller Christensen et al. (2019)	Forecast accuracy	Forecast Technology
2	Rossi et al. (2021), Liljestrand (2016)	Logistics Model	Logistics Technology
1	Salinas Segura et al. (2017)	Sensor-based	
1	Haass et al. (2015)	Autonomous - intelligent container	
1	Bertolini et al. (2013)	RFID in FIFO policy	Management Technology
1	Ribeiro et al. (2018)	Sustainable business model	
5	Rodrigues et al. (2020), Mullick et al. (2020), Moltene & Orsato (2020), Ciulli et al. (2019), Cane & Parra (2020)	Marketing digital platform	Marketing Technology
2	Oltra-Mestre et al. (2020), Ruggieri et al. (2020)	Industry 4.0 of process innovation	Process/
1	Garre et al. (2020)	Machine learning-production planning	production Technology
1	Fabbri et al. (2018)	Ultrasonic humidification	
1	Verghese et al. (2017)	Co-designing resource efficiency	
1	Bogataj et al. (2017)	Cyber-physical system in MRP model	
1	Wikstrom et al. (2013)	Packaging system	
2	Mirabella et al. (2013), Simms et al. (2019)	Recycling technologies	
1	Pfaltzgraff et al. (2013)	Biorefinery	
1	De Corato & Cancellara (2019)	Processing technology	
1	Li & Wang (2017)	Networked sensor data	Supply Chain Technology
1	Andreopoulou (2017)	IoT and food circular economy	
2	Irani et al. (2017), Wang et al. (2015)	Big data	
2	Kamilaris et al. (2019), Kamath (2018)	Blockchain	
1	Bottani et al. (2018)	Routing and location model	Transportation Technology

Most initiatives were conducted in the production (11) and supply chain areas (6). Process technology in North countries had led to the concept of a circular economy that minimizes waste and recycles production waste. Some frontier technologies had started to be applied in the process, such as the Industry 4.0-related technologies, cyber systems, and machine learning. There are some studies related to blockchain technology employed in the supply chain area (Kamilaris et al., 2019; Kamath, 2018), and one study discussed IoT and the relationship between its use in the food supply chain and the circular economy (Andreopoulou, 2017). Digital technology such as blockchain technology brings transparency and traceability to the food supply chain, although there were some challenges in technical aspects such as education, policies and regulations which were still inadequate (Kamilaris et al., 2019). A case study of Walmart Food Safety Collaboration Center conducted by Kamath (2018) described the success stories of the retail store network in implementing two blockchain pilot projects on pork supply chain in China and mangoes chain in US. Good collaboration with stakeholders and regulatory support that provides a positive climate are the keys to Walmart's success in adopting technology.

Studies on the use of marketing technology (5) in North countries discussed marketing platforms that were commonly used in developed countries. In other words, the use of the food-marketing platform had entered a mature level in developed countries. Mullick et al. (2020) stated in their study that the use of digital platforms may reduce the food waste rates through a relationship between retailers and their customer's activities, known as cross-side network effects. Similar result was also revealed by Moltene and Orsato (2021) by analysing the sharing economy on digital platforms through activities such as donations, sales and food exchange between institutions. The existence of a digital platform that had taken a brokerage function in the food supply chain fosters the recovery of waste by transfer and recovery of discarded resources between supply chain actors (Ciulli et al., 2019; Cane & Parra, 2020). More than just discussing the impact of using a food sales online platform, the study of Rodrigues et al. (2020) proposed a food waste minimization and mitigation framework using social, economic and environmental metrics attributes. They used the level of food losses, CO₂ and water as the environmental metrics, direct losses and opportunity cost as economic metrics, and food poverty relief as a social metric.

Many studies had also analyzed preventive actions to reduce waste that may occur in households (Rodrigues et al., 2020; Wikstrom et al., 2013; Mullick et al., 2020; Moltene & Orsato, 2020; Ciulli et al., 2019; Cane & Parra, 2020; Liljestrang, 2016; Yu & Nagurney, 2013). Sustainability had been an issue in North countries' studies; hence, some studies discussed the relationship between food loss and food waste on environmental impacts by reducing carbon emissions (Haass et al., 2015), eco-innovation (Simms et al., 2019), and utilization of ultrasonic humidification (Fabbri et al., 2018). The autonomous control system of intelligent containers had been a research topic that reflected the capabilities of future systems (Haass et al., 2015).

Table 5 shows the clustering of technology-based initiatives to control FLW in South countries. The cluster with the largest number of studies is logistics technology (7), which mostly

discusses cold-chain management. The study of Raut et al. (2019) revealed two factors that influenced the high post-harvest loss in India, namely the inavailability of refrigerated vehicles and excessive loading on the vehicles which cause the barriers of food transportation. Food cold chain has been a critical issue in managing FLW, which was illustrated by Shashi et al. (2020), indicated the negative impacts due to poor cold chain management. Integration of an Internet of Things and multi-temperature delivery planning was recommended in the study conducted by Tsang et al. (2020) as an alternative solution to meet the needs of food shipments at various temperatures. The system allows the re-routing of delivery plan, once unexpected incidents were detected by the IoT technologies.

Table 5: Technology Applied In Initiatives in South Countries (Brazil, China, India, Bangladesh, Hongkong, Lithuania, Sub Saharan Africa, and Columbia, Romania)

Number of Publications	Reference	Technology applied in initiatives	Cluster of Technology
2	Priyadarshi et al. (2019), Gruzaukas et al. (2019)	Forecast accuracy technique	Forecast Technology
3	Raut et al. (2019), Shashi et al. (2020), Tsang et al. (2020)	Food cold chain management	Logistics Technology
1	Tedla et al. (2019)	Automation system for storage houses	
1	Lanfranchi et al. (2016)	RFID system	
2	Gardas et al. (2018), Chan et al. (2020)	Structural Optimization Modelling in Logistics	
2	De Souza et al. (2021), Gustavo et al. (2021)	Green and innovative marketing	
1	Paulikiene et al. (2020)	Ozone technology	Process/production Technology
2	Balamurugan et al. (2020), Kumar et al. (2021)	Automation in production	
1	Kumar et al. (2020)	Information & Communication Technology	Supply Chain Technology
1	Kaur et al. (2019)	IoT based supply chain traceability	
1	Wang et al. (2015)	Big data	
2	Liu et al. (2021), Orjuela-Castro et al. (2019)	Routing model	Transportation Technology
1	Al Amin et al. (2021)	Delivery application	

Automation is one of the topics discussed in several studies on both the logistics and production processes. While North countries have already applied autonomous systems, South countries are still lagging in the implementation of automation. The difference factor between ‘automation’ and ‘autonomous’ is the level of direct human control in the system during operation (Norris & Patterson, 2019). An autonomous system would be able to make a self-response to unexpected events without human involvement, while automation systems are designed to accomplish certain tasks based on human decisions with some assumptions. Tedla et al. (2019) in their study in the Sub-Saharan region revealed that the automated granary monitoring and controlling system provides relevant and accurate information regarding the

granary status. The information plays an important role in maintaining grain quality and will have an impact on the storage loss reduction.

Some studies in South countries have led to environmental considerations in green marketing topics. A multiple case study on several supermarkets conducted by Gustavo et al. (2021) concluded that green marketing actions should be implemented in both conventional and digitized actions in order to leverage sales, leading to reduced food waste. Some similarities were found in the types of technology applied in the North and South, namely Big Data in the supply chain and RFID technology in the logistics area. The routing model has also been a topic in both North and South countries.

Challenges in the adoption of technology

Some obstacles to adopt the technology revealed in several studies are then classified as external and internal challenges. The factors considered in the external challenges are government support, technology risks, and market and supply chain risks. Capabilities, infrastructure availability, and financial risk are classified as internal challenges.

Table 6 shows the differences between external challenges in the North and South countries. A study in the UK and Netherlands discussed technology risks and market and supply chain risks as adoption challenges (Simms et al., 2019), while all three studies in India reviewed the lack of government support and incentives in the case of technology adoption (Wang et al., 2015; Gardas et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2021).

Table 6: External Challenges

Countries clusters	Reference	External Challenges		
		Government Support	Technology Risks	Market & Supply Chain Risks
North (UK & Netherlands)	Simms et al. (2019)	-	- Characteristics of waste-reducing technologies & their impact on the Product - High risk & unproven technologies - Lack of equal distribution of costs & benefits	- Retailing & point of sale risks - Lack of consumer market opportunity
South (India)	Gardas et al. (2018), Kumar et al. (2021), Wang et al. (2015)	- Lack of government support & incentives	-	-

Study conducted by Simms et al. (2019) revealed that the technology adoption in the food processing sector, as part of food supply chain, was not effective without simultaneous acceptance by both food processors and retailers. Most of the barriers to technology adoption in North countries were the perception of risk in the food supply chain actors, while external barriers in the South still lied in the supply chain ecosystem climate which was influenced by government policies and regulations.

The internal challenges that need to be resolved in the South are the lack of human resource capabilities and the reluctance to change by accepting a new culture of technology (Wang et al., 2015; Gardas et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2021), while North countries are facing environmental impacts due to FLW need supply chain capabilities that carry out environmentally friendly processes (Simms et al., 2019). The North countries also encounter a lack of consistent environmental guidance to develop this particular capability. Switching cost and unit cost impact are considered as financial risk of technology adoption.

Problems in infrastructure, lack of procedures and good practices, non-availability of refrigerated vehicles are some of the factors that hinder the technology adoption of food supply chain in South countries and give an impact on high FLW rate. Therefore, a fundamental improvement is needed to reduce FLW in the South, starting with the provision of adequate infrastructure and increasing the capability of human resources.

Table 7: Internal Challenges

Countries clusters	Reference	Internal Challenges		
		Capabilities	Infrastructure Availability	Financial Risk
North: UK & Netherlands	Simms et al. (2019)	- Poor Communication & Adversarial Relationship - Lack of required Environmental Capabilities	Lack of Consistent Environmental Guidance	Switching cost & Unit Cost impact
South: India	Gardas et al. (2018), Kumar et al. (2021), Wang et al. (2015)	- Lack of skilled workforce and digital environment - Lack of competency & motivation - Lack of awareness & acceptance - Fear of change in culture - Lack of proper training about Green Supply Chain	- Lack of physical & IT infrastructure - Lack of effective policy & protocol - Lack of sustainable practices - Lack of circular design aspect - The non-availability of refrigerated vehicles	-

Future Study Directions

The keyword map in Fig.5 shows some clusters distinguished by colors based on the publication year of each article. The first cluster contained articles published around 2018, discussing the topics of supply chain management, decision making, and post-harvest loss-big data. The second cluster consists of articles published around 2019 and discusses the topics of supply chains, food waste, IoT, environmental impact, and sustainable development. The third cluster contained articles published around 2020, and the topics discussed are food loss, waste management, recycling, food security, and sustainability. It can be argued that previous studies have extensively discussed the relationship between the food supply chain, food losses, and waste, and their impact on the environment.

Recent studies tend to develop broad topic discussions in articles, namely the relationship between FLW, food security, and the sustainability of the food system, taking into consideration the economic, social, and environmental impacts of FLW. This future research trend is also triggered by the global issue of food security, which affects the sustainability of food systems.

Figure 5: Keywords Mapping Using VOS Viewer

From the mapping and analysis results of previous studies and looking at trends in future studies, there is still an opportunity for studies on FLW to be carried out, especially in South countries as developing countries. To understand the relationship between reducing FLW levels, circular economy, and food system sustainability, further FLW studies need to be conducted.

Proposed Conceptual Model

To answer the research gap that has been shown in the mapping result using the Vos Viewer application, the elements gathered from the analysis of literature are used to build a conceptual model described in the causal loop diagram, which can later be analyzed in future research. The conceptual model for adopting technology to reduce FLW is depicted in Fig 6. The proposed conceptual model consists of two types of loops: reinforcing loops (R) and balancing loops (B). Reinforcing loops add value to the achievement of system goals, whereas balancing loops reduce the value of its goals.

The relationships between the elements in the causal loop of the capability sub-model are represented by loop R1. Organizational capabilities related to technology adoption are affected by the knowledge of technologies that have an impact on FLW and organizational innovation

capabilities. Lack of operating capability also impacts production quality, logistics, processing, storage, packaging, and poor delivery (Simms et al., 2019), which are more prevalent in South countries. From the literature review findings, there are differences in the context of knowledge that is lacking in the South and North countries. Therefore, it is recommended to differentiate the models between these two economies types of countries.

Figure 6: Proposed Conceptual Model

Good organizational capabilities result in improved FLW performance, resulting in an efficient flow of goods and increased company profits. This profit can be used for investments in technology and increases the frequency of training as a result of the increasing training needs. Knowledge of technology improves as the training frequency increases. Lack of access to knowledge of FLW and technology; affects the organization’s food loss performance (Kumar et al, 2021; Kos & Kloppenburg, 2019).

Loop R2 revealed that improved food loss performance will increase organizational interest in technology, in addition to being influenced by the price of technology. This increasing interest will increase confidence in technology’s effectiveness. The high variety of technology might cause the problem of selecting the appropriate type to adopt, which can be avoided if the supply chain actors have knowledge of technology and its effectiveness for adequate use. Confidence in the technology’s effectiveness will increase the rate of technology adoption, which also affects food loss performance improvement at a unidirectional rate.

The infrastructure availability sub-model (loop R3) explains the relationship between infrastructure availability and the technology adoption rate. The adoption rate requires the necessary support infrastructure funded by investment funds. Inadequate infrastructure, in terms of both quantity and quality, affects the FLW performance of food supply chain actors (Raut et al. 2018). The need for infrastructure to support the applied technology drives technology investment. Access to funding also encourages technological investment, which ultimately increases the adoption rate.

Loops B1 and B2 balance the systems; these loops reduce the value of the system as constraints on the achievement of the goals. The decision to invest in technology is affected by people's perception of risk, financial risk, and risk from using technology; because the perception of high risk will reduce investment interest. Knowledge of technology and financial risks affect the perception of risks; hence, access to knowledge is very important.

The institutional sub-model is not described by a causal loop diagram; rather, it considers several elements, namely program objectives, the parameters of the objective assessment, activities needed to execute the programs, the effectivity measurement of all activities, and the institutions involved in implementing the programs.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study presents a categorization of technologies applied to reduce FLW initiatives and their adoption challenges in North and South countries, which are the terms used for developed and developing economies countries, to support food sustainability through food security as a direct impact of FLW reduction. A Systematic Literature Review was conducted and the report was divided into five parts as described before.

Based on the literature review results, the technology used in North countries is the latest Industry 4.0 technology which mostly applies to autonomous systems (i.e., sensor-based technology and intelligent containers). Meanwhile, most studies in South countries analyze the application of an automation system that still considers human involvement, that is, for example, the need for people for setting the coolant temperature in the cold chain system. Hence, it can be concluded that technological developments in South countries are lagging compared with those in North countries. This condition is reasonable because the challenges to implementing technology in South countries are more numerous and more basic than those faced by North countries. Lack of awareness, competency, and infrastructure are the main issues in South countries, while in North countries risk factors (technical risk, market risk, and financial risk) must be considered when adopting technology. Lack of government support is also a challenge for South countries, but this is not an issue for North countries.

A conceptual model of FLW management through technology adoption was proposed in this study based on the results obtained from the literature review. The proposed conceptual model can be the opportunity in future research to be compared to the real world by conducting some interviews, surveys, or focus group discussions with actors and stakeholders in a food supply chain; and the adjusted model may contribute to giving insights to decision-makers in increasing the rates of technology adoption in South countries. Refer to the target 12.3 of SDGs, the reduction of FLW in South countries may improve their economics of countries, cities, businesses, and households. The trend of research related to this topic is also useful for other researchers in the future to be able to conduct more in-depth research on FLW to gain the food system sustainability.

This review study also presents limitations, as the databases chosen for paper selection are few among the many available databases. The limited number of countries analyzed in previous

studies is also a limitation of this study, which can be an opportunity for improvement in future research.

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